

did some experimental work but conclusion on the independence of crack

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growth rate from the crack length is questionable. The work attempted is interesting in that it is necessary to explain why the crack grows in a very irregular manner and the rate is erratic

OBSERVATIONS ON TRANSVERSE PLY CRACK GROWTH IN A $(0/90_2)_S$ CFRP LAMINATE UNDER MONOTONIC AND CYCLIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Coupons from a CFRP $(0/90_2)_S$ laminate have been loaded in monotonic tension and in tension-tension fatigue at three different maximum stress levels. The development of transverse ply cracks was observed using penetrant-enhanced X-radiography and optical microscopy on polished sections from the coupons. The pattern of crack development was found to depend on the mode of loading and the stress level under cyclic loading.

INTRODUCTION

The response of fibre reinforced polymer composites to mechanical loading is complex. In continuous fibre reinforced laminates, matrix cracking initially occurs in the off-axis plies; this can lead to fibre breakage in adjacent longitudinal plies and, in addition, delamination between plies of different orientation.

Early work by Broutman and Sahu [1] showed that cracks accumulated in the transverse ply of GFRP crossply laminates loaded in fatigue, with a consequent reduction in stiffness. Reifsnider and co-workers [2,3] proposed a "characteristic damage state" based on observations that the crack pattern in any off-axis ply in a particular laminate reached a stable condition which was independent of load history and other variables such as environment.

A number of authors have attempted to formulate damage growth laws for matrix cracking under different loading conditions using a fracture mechanics approach. Wang et al [4] used a model based on the strain

energy release rate of a crack growing across the thickness of the transverse ply, having initially spanned the laminate width. Poursartip et al [5] integrated expressions for the rate of damage accumulation, quantified by measurements of compliance change with cycling, to predict fatigue life. Ogin et al [6] and Ogin and Smith [7] applied an alternative fracture mechanics model to predict stiffness reduction with cycles at different load levels in a $(0/90)_S$ GFRP laminate; crack growth across the width of the laminate is governed by a stress intensity factor which depends on crack spacing and transverse ply thickness but is independent of crack length. Figure 1 shows the envisaged stress trajectories around the tip of a transverse ply crack according to this model. Over most of the length of the crack the load is transferred into the 0° plies by shear and therefore does not build up at the crack tip. There is, however, a stress intensity due to the localised stress disturbance at the crack which scales with the transverse ply thickness. This crack growth model was applied to fatigue growth of transverse ply cracks in $(0/90_2)_S$ GFRP and $(0/90_3)_S$ CFRP laminates (Ogin et al [8]). In this work, attention is focussed on crack growth for different cyclic loading levels.

Figure 1 Three-dimensional model of a growing transverse ply crack showing the stress distribution along the crack and near the crack tip, T.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The (0/90₂)_S CFRP laminate was fabricated from Ciba-Geigy XA-S/914 prepreg with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125mm. Coupons 200mm long and 20mm wide were loaded monotonically and under fatigue conditions with R=0.1 at a frequency of 10Hz; the cyclic loading levels were chosen to be below, slightly above and well above the static cracking threshold of ≈ 325 MPa (about 0.6% applied strain).

The growth of transverse ply cracks was monitored at intervals during the tests using penetrant-enhanced X-radiography, and crack density measurements were obtained from the resulting photographs. The number of transverse cracks was counted at their intersection with both of the coupon edges and with a line down the centre of the coupon. Complete infiltration of the zinc iodide penetrant was ensured by applying the solution to both edges of the coupon whilst under a small applied load for at least 30 minutes; the exposure was made at a tube voltage of 26 kV for 2 minutes on very fine grained X-ray film.

The X-radiograph technique is dependent on the dye penetrant infiltrating the cracks from the free edge, and therefore it cannot detect damage which does not intersect the edge. In order to detect transverse ply cracks which might cross the centre of the laminate but not intersect either free edge, some coupons were sectioned longitudinally down their centre and X-radiographs taken of each of the two pieces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The series of X-radiographs in Figures 2-5 show the development of transverse ply cracking under monotonic loading (Fig. 2) and under fatigue loading at $\sigma_{\max} = 235$ MPa (Fig. 3a), 360 MPa (Fig. 4) and 500 MPa (Fig.5).

Under monotonic loading up to the onset of longitudinal ply failure, all of the transverse cracks span the entire width of the laminate (see Fig. 2). The crack density increases with increasing applied stress (indicated at one cycle in Fig. 7), attaining a final spacing of approximately one transverse ply thickness before fracture of the coupon.

scale 5mm

Figure 2 X-radiograph showing a coupon after monotonic loading close to failure (≈ 570 MPa)

Under cyclic loading, when σ_{\max} is below the static cracking threshold of ≈ 325 MPa (see Fig. 3), cracks initiate at the coupon edge and grow very slowly (i.e. over periods of several thousands of cycles) across the width of the laminate throughout the test. This contrasts with the rapid crack growth observed in the early stages of the test when σ_{\max} is just above the static threshold (see Fig. 4) where most new cracks appear to span the width instantaneously; however, as the crack spacing decreases later in the test, slow crack growth is also observed.

scale 5mm

10 000

CYCLES

100 000

CYCLES

500 000

CYCLES

Figure 3 Series of X-radiographs showing the development of transverse cracks during cyclic loading at $\sigma_{\max} = 235$ MPa

scale 5mm

500

CYCLES

10 000

CYCLES

200 000

CYCLES

Figure 4 Series of X-radiographs showing the development of transverse cracks during cyclic loading at $\sigma_{\max} = 360$ MPa

When σ_{\max} is high compared to the static threshold (Fig. 5), cracks grow rapidly across the complete width of the coupon, attaining a very high density within a few hundred cycles. Cracks initiated after approximately 500 cycles grow slowly across the width of the coupon at a rate which depends on the local crack spacing. At this stress, there is 0/90 delamination and longitudinal ply splitting by the final stage of the test, i.e. 300 000 cycles.

Figure 5 Series of X-radiographs showing the development of transverse cracks during cyclic loading at $\sigma_{\max} = 500$ MPa

These results may be interpreted in the following way: fast fracture occurred when the instantaneous stress intensity was greater than the fracture toughness for matrix cracking, i.e. in static loading where the applied stress progressively increases, and in the early stages of fatigue at the higher load level when the crack spacing is large. Slow crack growth occurred when the stress intensity was lower than the fracture toughness, i.e. throughout fatigue loading at the low level, and in fatigue at the high level as the crack spacing decreased (due to the dependence of the stress intensity on the crack spacing [6]).

Figure 6 shows optical micrographs of polished edge sections from coupons loaded monotonically and in fatigue. Under monotonic loading (see Fig. 6a), cracks spanned the thickness of the transverse ply, without delamination at the intersection of the crack with the 0/90 interface. The appearance of transverse ply cracks in the fatigue coupons loaded at $\sigma_{\max} = 235$ MPa and 360 MPa is similar to the monotonic crack pattern. At $\sigma_{\max} = 500$ MPa (see Fig. 6b), in addition to the type of transverse cracks observed under the other loading conditions, short cracks develop running from the 0/90 interface at an angle of about 45° towards the primary

transverse cracks. The short cracks initiate from fibre/matrix debonds at the 0/90 interface at a regular distance of approximately one half of the transverse ply thickness either side of the primary crack; they grow up to half way across the thickness of the transverse ply but do not appear to intersect with the primary cracks.

Figure 6 Micrographs showing edge cracking in coupons loaded to
(a) ≈ 570 MPa, monotonic (b) $\sigma_{\max} = 500$ MPa, 300 000 cycles

This form of angled crack was also observed in a similar CFRP (0/90₃)_S laminate under fatigue loading at stress levels just above the monotonic transverse ply cracking threshold [9]. These cracks developed after a high density of primary transverse cracks was attained (greater than the maximum density seen in a static test); microscopy on the pre-polished edges of the coupons was correlated with their appearance on the X-radiographs as very short, indistinct lines compared to the primary cracks (see Fig. 5).

Figure 7 shows the number of cracks at the edge and centre against cycles for the three fatigue stress levels used as well as for the monotonic tests. At the lowest fatigue stress ($\sigma_{\max} = 235$ MPa), there is an incubation period of between 10^3 and 10^4 cycles before transverse ply cracking occurs and none of the cracks has grown past the centre of the coupon at 10^4 cycles. The crack density at the free edge increases continuously with increasing cycles and the difference in crack density at the edge and centre of the coupon reflects the slow growth of cracks across the coupon width. It may be expected that the lines would converge at longer fatigue lives since a maximum number of cracks will be initiated at the edge, which then propagate gradually across the coupon width. This maximum may have a dependence on loading level.

Figure 7 Number of transverse ply cracks at the edge and centre-line vs cycles for fatigue at $\sigma_{\max} = 500$ MPa, 360 MPa, 235 MPa and monotonic loading.

At the intermediate stress level ($\sigma_{\max} = 360$ MPa), the edge and centre-line crack densities are initially coincident, diverging after several hundred cycles when the predominant mode of cracking changes from fast growth to slow growth as the crack spacing decreases. The centre-line crack density should also approach the edge density with increasing number of cycles, and coincide earlier than at the lower stress.

At the highest stress level ($\sigma_{\max} = 500$ MPa), some transverse ply cracks initiate on the first cycle. The initial crack density (at the edge) at one cycle is plotted together with the crack densities measured in coupons loaded monotonically up to stresses close to failure. For the fatigue specimen, the initial centre-line crack density is unexpectedly low and is considered to be suspect, since cracks were observed to span the full width of all coupons loaded monotonically, even at stresses lower than 500 MPa. The edge and centre-line crack density lines converge within the first 50 cycles (i.e. cracks predominantly span the coupon width) and begin to diverge when slow growth of newly initiated cracks occurs. The tendency for the lines to converge at a higher number of cycles is opposed by the development of the secondary form of transverse cracks (Fig. 6b) which occurs at this fatigue stress. These cracks initiate after approximately 5000 cycles, as inferred by the appearance on the X-radiographs at this stage of short indistinct cracks. They contribute to the density of cracks measured at the edges of the coupon but only grow very slowly across the width of the coupon compared with the primary transverse cracks. Therefore, the edge density line in Figure 7 diverges further from the centre density line.

Very different crack distributions are observed under monotonic and cyclic loading. At each of the fatigue stress levels there is a greater crack density at both the edges and the centre than in the static test. In particular, there are more cracks per unit length towards the edges of the coupon under cyclic loading. The current work on the $(0/90_2)_5$ laminate further suggests a dependence of crack pattern on laminate load history, and implies that the characteristic damage state concept does not fully describe the saturation damage pattern for every load history.

The additional radiography of the tested coupon after sectioning suggested that all the transverse cracks initiated at the edge, since no internal transverse ply cracks were revealed by X-radiography of the sections. This contrasts with observations on the fatigue growth of transverse ply cracks in GFRP [6] and KFRP [10] where crack initiation away from coupon edges has been observed.

CONCLUSIONS

The pattern of crack development depended on the load level and the mode of loading:

monotonic loading of the ply	fast fracture across the complete width
cyclic load below static cracking threshold	slow growth across the width of the ply
cyclic load near threshold	initially fast fracture then slow crack growth due to the decreased crack spacing
cyclic load above threshold	initially fast fracture then slow crack growth, slow-growing secondary cracks develop after many cycles

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